

Deconstructing Disinformation through Western and Indian epistemological lenses and constructs

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Keywords

[Disinformation, Indian Epistemological lenses, Western Epistemological Constructs, Philosophy of Disinformation, Aristotelian Theory of Deviance, Le Bon's Contagion Theory]

STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of your contribution

The aim is to develop a theoretical construct for the conceptualization of disinformation through the untold stories of the Indian Epistemological construct of *Pramāṇa* and Floridi's Philosophy of Information and Aristotelian Theory of Deviance.

Value of your contribution

The disinformation phenomenon has risen to a crisis level, impacting our society in myriad ways. A theoretical construct helps in conceptualizing and confronting it better. It shines a light on the Indian Epistemological construct of Six *Pramāṇas* (seeking proof) (an untold story in deconstructing disinformation). The audience will learn to conceptualize disinformation within this construct. This understanding helps develop methods of detecting disinformation and minimizing this scourge.

Research outline

This paper conceptualizes disinformation using the Indian Epistemological construct of *Pramāṇa* (seeking proof) and Floridi's Philosophy of Information. I posit that disinformation is deviant behavior framing it within the Aristotelian Theory of Deviance. Postulate that Le Bon's contagion theory and the concept of Networked Individuality can explicate the epidemiology of disinformation.

According to Fallis (2015), information may be inaccurate due to an honest mistake, negligence, unconscious bias, or intentional deception. When inaccuracy is intended

for deception, it is disinformation; otherwise, it is misinformation. Expanding this notion of disinformation, I deconstruct disinformation through the following constructs.

1. Disinformation is unvalidated information (without proof)

Indian epistemology (Bilimoria, 1993) recognizes Six *Pramāṇas*—methods of obtaining valid knowledge. They are: *Pratyakṣa* (perception); *Anumāna* (inference); *Upamāna* (comparison/analogy); *Arthāpatti* (postulation); *Anupalabdi* (non-perception or negative/cognitive proof); *Śabda* (word, a testimony of past or present reliable experts). *Pramāṇa* (Sanskrit: “measure”) in Indian philosophy is how one obtains accurate and valid knowledge about the world. *Pramāṇas* offer a framework for defining disinformation as unvalidated information/information without proof.

2. Disinformation is an outcome of a defective process

I frame the conceptualization of disinformation using Floridi’s philosophy of information (2011). Though he does not define disinformation, Floridi argues that we need to study what happens when “the information process is defective”. Deriving from this construct, I argue that disinformation is an outcome of a defective method of creating, processing, managing, and using the information with an intent to mislead.

3. Disinformation is Deviance

I frame ‘intent to mislead’ as deviant behaviour. Aristotle’s Theory of Deviance (Prus, 2015) is developed from Aristotle’s *Nicomachean Ethics* and *Rhetoric* (study of community-based knowing and acting and persuasive interchange and contested reality). Accordingly, all instances of knowing and acting must be comprehended within the interchanges and interconnected contexts of human group life. I argue that disinformation is deemed a community-based knowing and activity and studied as persuasive interchange within a community.

4. Disinformation is a Social Contagion

Le Bon (1895) formulated the contagion theory to explain crowd behavior and argued that crowds exert a hypnotic influence over their members, leading large numbers of them to abandon personal responsibility and surrender to the contagious emotions of the crowd. As Sampson (2012) states, the contagion theory of Le Bon and Tarde explains the tendency for emotions and effects to spread “accidentally” on digital networks. I argue that disinformation is a social contagion.

5. Networked Individuality, Social Networks, and Disinformation

A fundamental feature of the Information Age is its reliance on networks as the key feature of social morphology (Castells, 2010). Integrating individuality and sociality in digital networks, Adolf and Deicke (2014) posit that the “Networked Individuality” (NI) is the point where the societal process of continuing individualization converges with the increasingly important network mode of mediated communication. I argue that disinformation is due to NI and network effects.

Thus, I develop the construct that disinformation is unvalidated information/information without proof and an outcome of a defective process. Disinformation is deviant behaviour, and its epidemiology is consequent to the social network effects. The Contagion Theory and Networked Individuality concepts help explicate the disinformation phenomenon.

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